

G'aniyeva Nigora Olimbekovna

School 1 in Margilon

Abstract. This article discusses the main directions characteristic of the current stage of development of cognitive linguistics in the USA and Western Europe, and examines the main cognitive units used in the works of Western cognitive linguists.

Keywords: frames, concepts, domains, idealized cognitive models, conceptualization processes.

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive linguistics, which focuses on language as a tool for organizing, processing and transmitting information, is an approach to natural language analysis that emerged in the late 70s and early 80s.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cognitive linguistics as an independent field of linguistics originates in the works of Western linguists J. Lakoff, R. Lancker, L. Talmy, C. Fillmore. Research in the same direction was carried out by their colleagues and students, among whom are J. Fauconnier, I. Sweetser, M. Johnson, M. Turner, R. Gibbs, B. Croft, A. Goldberg, D. Tuggy, L. Yandu, S. Rice, R. Maldonado, K. von Hoek, D. Geeraerts, H. Kuykens. The ideas of cognitive linguistics in Western and Central Europe were picked up and developed by a number of scientists: R. Dirven, B. Rudzka-Austin, D. Taylor, K. Singh, A. Verhagen, B. Lewandowska-Tomaszczuk, P. Harder, G. Radden [9, p. 21].

Over the past three decades, cognitive linguistics has become one of the most dynamically developing areas of research within theoretical and descriptive linguistics, changing its status from “revolutionary” to “generally accepted.” It

considers most of the issues that have been dealt with by general linguistics - from phonology and pragmatics to syntax and semantics, incorporating some aspects of such sciences as developmental psychology - language acquisition, neuropsychology - embodied consciousness, neurobiology - the work of mechanisms thinking, social psychology – language in social interaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The material of study in linguocognitology is language. British scientist J. Taylor says that language “is an integral part of human cognition, and the analysis of any phenomena in language should be based on knowledge about human cognitive activity, i.e. cognitive linguistics is knowledge not about language, but knowledge gained through language. It is necessary to study language in the light of what is known about thinking using various research methods - be it experiment, introspection, or simply everyday observation”. The editors of the journal *Cognitive Linguistics Research* define cognitive linguistics as follows: cognitive linguistics includes a wide range of issues and a number of compatible theoretical approaches, which are based on one idea - language as one of the facets of cognition reflects social, cultural, psychological, communicative and functional aspects and can only be understood in the context of a realistic view of its acquisition, cognitive development and mental processes. She seeks to explain the structure of language through concepts inherent in other cognitive mechanisms to which she refers, along with its communicative function.

Cognitive linguistics is a cluster of mutually compatible and complementary approaches [9, p. 21]. Thus, within the framework of cognitive linguistics, three large areas of research are distinguished:

1) *approaches to the study of grammar* that study language at the structural and organizational levels. These include cognitive grammar (R. Lanecker, L. Talmy) and construction grammar (C. Fillmore, P. Kay, A. Goldberg, J. Lakoff, W. Croft, B. Bergen);

2) *cognitive semantics*, which through language examines various aspects of human mental activity, such as the representation of knowledge and the construction of meanings. Cognitive semantics includes the theory of conceptual metaphor (J. Lakoff, M. Johnson, R. Gibbs, M. Turner), the theory of mental spaces (J. Fauconnier, B. Dansiger, S. Coulson), the theory conceptual integration (or confusion) (J. Fauconnier, M. Turner), as well as such an approach as cognitive lexical semantics, within the framework of which the theory of fundamental polysemy and the theory of lexical concepts and cognitive models were developed (V. Evans, A. Theiler) [6, p. 462 – 469];

3) *an integrative approach*, which involves solving a research problem by using the developments of the two areas indicated above (W. Evans, A. Theiler, E. Sweetser).

In general, among the main issues considered in the works of Western cognitive linguists, D. Geeraerts and H. Kuykens list the following:

- structural characteristics of categorization in natural languages (for example, prototypicality, systematic polysemy, cognitive models, mental images, metaphor);
- functional principles of linguistic organization (iconicity and naturalness);
- conceptual interaction between syntax and semantics (considered within the framework of cognitive and construction grammars);
- empirical and pragmatic foundations of the language used;
- the connection between language and thought, including questions about relativism and conceptual universals [9, p. 4].

In Western cognitive linguistics today there is no consensus regarding the basic units of research. Each area of cognitive research has developed its own terminological apparatus, but many terms have become widespread and are analyzed in most or all theories [2; 4]. As T. Klosner and W. Croft write, there is also variability in the names of the same theoretical constructs within different approaches. For example [2, p. 4] (table).

Table 1.

Scientists	Variants of terms used to refer to theoretical constructs		
T. Klozner, W. Croft	concept	domain	conceptualization processes
R. Laneker	profile	basis, domain	focal setting, conceptualization processes, conceptualization
J. Lakoff	concept	ICM, domain	metaphor, metonymy, figurative scheme, transformation
C. Fillmore	concept	frame	
L. Talmy			image forming systems

A. Chenki, summarizing the available research on cognitive constructs, which are verbalized structures of knowledge, names three cognitive units: frames, idealized cognitive models and domains [1, p. 170]. At the same time, he notes that it can be very difficult to attribute a construct to a frame, idealized cognitive model (ICM) or domain due to their cognitive nature, therefore it is necessary to take into account contextual factors as well as the subjective essence of the construct. The terms “frame”, “ICM”, “domain” can refer to the structure of knowledge that serves as the background for interpreting the meaning of linguistic forms, so there are overlaps in how they are used by researchers [1, p. 184].

J. Lakoff names 5 main types of ICM: propositional, schematic-figurative, metaphorical, metonymic, symbolic.

Propositional models are associated with really existing objects, their properties and relationships with each other. However, this connection cannot be called direct, since cognitive models representing objects and relationships between them are mental constructs and do not directly correlate with fragments of reality. In turn, J. Lakoff points out that the propositional structure of ICM can be of several types: simple proposition, scenario, set of features, taxonomy, radial category.

A simple proposition consists of a proof and a predicate. More complex examples involve operations from logical theory, such as quantification, conjunction, negation, etc. Propositional ICM, structured like a script, involves an

initial state, a sequence of events and a final state, as well as states and activities people whose goal-setting structures events.

If a set of features is a set of certain characteristics, then a propositional ICM structured in this way is nothing more than a “classical category” that has clear boundaries that are determined by the characteristics common to all its members. This is the so-called a naive model of how categories work, and what is very often resorted to in everyday reasoning - “categorical statements”, which involve uniform statements about all members of the category representing a given type of reasoning.

M. Johnson, describing the figurative scheme as “a repeating dynamic typical model of our perceptual interactions and motor programs, which gives our experience structure and logic”, proposed about 30 figurative schemes, which he considered significant: *container, balance, blocking, removing restrictions, lifting a ban, attraction, set-account, path, connection, center-periphery, cycle, close-far, scale, part-whole, etc.*

The two main contexts in which the concept of domain is used as a theoretical construct in cognitive linguistics are conceptual metaphor theory and cognitive grammar. J. Lakoff writes that projection in conceptual metaphors occurs between two “domains of experience,” where the target domain is understood through the source domain. Moreover, the concept of a domain used in the theory of conceptual metaphors is somewhat broader than domains in mental spaces, since mental spaces imply conceptualization by an individual within a specific context for specific purposes, while domains absorb many associated general aspects of experience, which are also conceptualized [1, p. 181].

The need to organize concepts was understood by many researchers, which led to the emergence of the terms “frame”, “scheme”, “script”, “pseudotext”, “cognitive model”, “gestalt”, “base”, “scene” [3, p. 8], since concepts are not isolated, atomic units of the mind, but phenomena that exist and are perceived in the context of the assumed background structures of knowledge. The most general

designation for these background knowledge structures is the concept of domain [2, p. 2].

CONCLUSION

Categories, according to W. Croft, have an internal structure, which is called a prototypical structure, and which is characterized by the connection between its internal elements and taxonomic relationships between the categories themselves [2, p. 3]. Thus, the main fundamental units of structured knowledge identified by Western researchers in cognitive linguistics include frames, idealized cognitive models, domains, concepts, conceptualization processes and categorical structures.

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